

Continental pedoclimatic region

Location

Germany (North Rhine–Westphalia – Nideggen;
Saxony–Anhalt – Trippigleben)

Key Issues

- » **Intensive agriculture** dominated by **wheat** and **potatoes**.
- » Increasing **fungal infestation** (e.g., *Fusarium*, *Alternaria*) and presence of **mycotoxins** harmful to human and animal health.
- » Extensive use of **fungicides** and **intensive tillage**, including in organic systems.
- » Risk of **fungicide resistance**, **groundwater contamination**, and **food chain accumulation**.
- » Urgent need for **natural bioregulation** and **sustainable alternatives**.

SoildiverAgro Approach

- » **Clover undersowing** supports soil fauna and yields (with suitable species).
- » **Biostimulants** improve biodiversity; **no revenue gain**.
- » **Broad undersowing** reduces disease better than strip.
- » **Risk of yield loss** if crops compete.
- » **More research** needed on mixtures.

Benefits

- » **Clover undersowing** enhances **natural fungal control**.
- » **Biostimulants** promote **biodiversity** and improve **soil health**.
- » **Broad undersowing** increases **fungal diversity** and strengthens **crop resilience**.
- » Reduction in **soil** and **water pollution**.
- » Supports the **optimization of ecosystem services**.

Within the Continental pedoclimatic region, three case studies were carried out as part of the **SoildiverAgro** Project in the German Federal States of North Rhine–Westphalia (near the city of Nideggen) and Saxony–Anhalt (close to Trippigleben). Both areas are characterized by intensive agricultural activity, with wheat and potatoes being the typical crops.

In wheat and potato cultivation in the Continental region, increasing agricultural challenges have emerged in recent years due to rising **infestation pressure from soil-borne and mycotoxin-producing plant pathogenic fungi** such as *Fusarium* and *Alternaria*. Such fungal infections lead to disease symptoms in the crops and potentially to contamination of harvested wheat grains and potato tubers with mycotoxins, which are hazardous to human and animal health. Consequently, **both yield levels and quality are reduced**. To prevent this scenario, **large quantities of external inputs are currently used** – primarily fungicides in conventional farming, and low-dose copper-based contact fungicides combined with intensive tillage in organic production. However, these practices are also problematic, as **fungicides can potentially enter the soil or groundwater, accumulate in the food chain, or lead to the development of fungicide resistance**, resulting in the emergence of new pathotypes that are even more difficult to control. Against this background, alternative measures are urgently required.

In this context, the ecosystem services provided by fungivorous soil fauna communities and their associated microorganisms represent a promising approach, as these organisms can act as antagonists, counteracting fungal infections and reducing mycotoxin concentrations in plant material. Microarthropods (collembolans and mites) exhibit great potential for natural bioregulation.

Considering these challenges for sustainable agriculture, the following management measures were implemented on the experimental fields and their impacts analyzed:

- a) **Extensification** (wider seed rows and no plant protection products) **and diversification** (clover undersowing) in **conventional wheat cultivation**.
- b) Application of a **plant biostimulant and a plant adjuvant** in conventional wheat cultivation.
- c) Use of **undersowing in organic potato** production (techniques: strip undersowing [only in furrows] vs. broad undersowing [across furrows and ridges]).

The main objectives of these practices were to identify management adjustments that allow a reduction in the application rates of fungicides while simultaneously promoting antagonistic soil microarthropods and their natural potential for the bioregulation of fungi and mycotoxins. Ideally, the practices would promote overall soil biodiversity, which is expected to have a positive effect on soil health, yield capacity, and resilience in the long term, and additionally ensure stable, high-level yields. In addition to reducing soil and water pollution, a reduction in external inputs is also expected to lower production costs, thereby increasing farmers' profitability.

Results

Based on the results obtained in this project, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. **Promote the use of clover undersowing in wheat cultivation to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities as antagonists of soil-borne fungal plant pathogens.** From an agroecological perspective, this practice promotes soil biodiversity, and the ecosystem services it provides; from an agroeconomic perspective, it has a positive legacy effect on crop revenue and profitability. However, attention must be paid to the composition of the clover species: suitable species include yellow clover and birdsfoot trefoil, while white and red clover are unsuitable, as they may serve as host plants for certain fungal plant pathogens, such as some *Fusarium* species.
2. **Promote the use of plant biostimulants in combination with plant adjuvants in wheat cultivation to enhance the diversity of collembolans, thereby contributing to a broader range of ecosystem services and**

the suppression of soil-borne fungal plant pathogens. From an agroecological perspective, plant biostimulants in combination with adjuvants have the potential to compensate for reduced fungicide applications and enhance plant and soil health. However, no impact on crop revenue is expected from an agroeconomic perspective based on current findings.

3. **Promote the use of undersowing in organic potato cultivation to improve soil conditions and support microarthropods and fungal saprotrophs and the ecosystem services they provide, such as reducing plant disease incidence.** From an agroecological perspective, positive effects on soil biodiversity are expected during the year of cultivation, though no legacy effect is anticipated if conventional tillage is subsequently applied. From an agroeconomic perspective, it is important to ensure that the undersown plants do not compete with the cultivated crop in order to avoid negative effects on yield levels.
4. **The broad undersowing technique should be prioritised when implementing undersowing in potato cultivation,** as this technique increases fungal diversity – including saprotrophs– and has the potential to reduce plant diseases. Broad undersowing is more beneficial to soil fauna, saprotrophic fungi, and crops than strip undersowing.
5. **It is recommended to support further research on alternative undersowing mixtures due to their potential to promote fungal antagonists and suppress plant-pathogenic fungi.**

From the **SoildiverAgro** project's perspective, implementing these policy recommendations could, in the long term, help to maintain soil health, promote soil biodiversity and optimize the use of the ecosystem services it provides in this region. The resilience and sustainability of agricultural systems could be promoted in this way. Overall, the measures have the potential to contribute to the reduction of soil and water pollution and thus to the reduction of risks to the environment and human health.

